

Note on an Attempted Synthesis of β -3-Amino-phenyl-ethylamine.

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In connection with certain investigation relating to phenanthrene alkaloids proceeding in this laboratory it became necessary to prepare 3-amino-phenyl-ethylamine.* This interesting substance seems to be unknown and hence it was thought worth while to synthesise it. For this purpose after a number of trials the following scheme was followed :

The compound at stage II, is described as a bright yellow substance (Tiemann and Oppermann, *Ber.*, 1880, 13, 2060), m.p. 196-197° but it is now found to be colourless and melts at 200°-201°. The

* It was the intention to utilise the β -amino grouping for a Pictet and the nuclear NH_2 for a Pictor synthesis, thereby producing a phenanthrenois-quinoline of the type of *apo*-morphine or dicentrine.

reduction (stage III) is done without difficulty; the compound melted at 180° (*cf.* Tiemann and Oppermann, (*loc. cit.*), who gives m.p. 180° - 181°). The acetylation (IV) is done in the usual way. For reduction (stage V), 2½% sodium amalgam is used. Compounds IV and V are now described for the first time. Unfortunately it was not found possible to prepare the amide either from the chloride of the acid or from its ester.

Hence it was thought that the amine would be better prepared if the condensation product of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and nitromethane be reduced.

But unfortunately this could not be done. An attempt was made to reduce it catalytically by palladium and hydrogen. This also failed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

m-Nitro-cinnamic Acid (II).—A mixture of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (20 g.), malonic acid (25 g.), pyridine (70 c.c.), piperidine (5 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath for an hour. The product is taken in water (400 c.c.) and is acidified with hydrochloric acid the precipitated nitrocinnamic acid is filtered and well washed. The product crystallises in colourless needles, m.p. 201 - 202° . (Found : N, 7.6. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires N, 7.9 per cent.)

m-Amino-cinnamic Acid (III).—Ferrous sulphate (180 g.) dissolved in water (450 c.c.) is treated with excess of liq. ammonia. The mixture is warmed on the water-bath to 90° and gradually a solution of nitro-cinnamic acid in ammonia is added with constant shaking. Not more than a few drops are taken in at a time. After the addition of the whole amount, the reaction is continued for 15 minutes on a boiling water-bath. Then it is filtered hot and the filtrate is carefully made very faintly acid with hydrochloric acid. The crystalline precipitate is collected after cooling. It is re-crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 180° . (Found: N, 8.4. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires N, 8.6 per cent.)

m-Acetyl-amino-cinnamic Acid (IV).—A mixture of amino-cinnamic acid (7 g.), acetic anhydride (25 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) was boiled for 2 hours. To the cold solution water was introduced till a slight turbidity was indicated. Then it was charcoaled, boiled and filtered. The filtrate deposited the acetyl derivative, m.p. 235°. Yield 5 gms. (pure product). (Found: N, 6.75. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.80 per cent.).

m-Acetyl-amino-hydrocinnamic Acid (V).—Acetylaminocinnamic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in 100 c.c. of dilute alkali. The solution was reduced with 2½ % sodium amalgam and was stirred mechanically. During the progress of the reduction, the free alkali in the reaction mixture was neutralised from time to time and at no time it was allowed to react strongly alkaline. The reduction was stopped when hydrogen freely bubbled out of the solution. During the reduction, the temperature of the mixture was not allowed to rise. The reduced acid was obtained on acidification. It was crystallised from hot dilute acetic acid in crusts, m.p. 162°. (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent.).

It was not possible either to esterify the above acid or prepare an amide.

m- ω -Dinitrostyrene—This compound was prepared by condensing *m*-nitro-benzaldehyde with nitromethane in cold absolute alcoholic solution with alcoholic KOH. *m*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (9 g.) and nitro-methane (4.2 g.) were dissolved in alcohol (14 c.c.). The solution was cooled to 0°. This was treated with a solution of KOH (9 g.) in 9 c.c. water and 12 c.c. alcohol, drop by drop. The reaction mixture is thoroughly stirred and at no time the temperature is allowed to rise higher than 5°. At the end of the reaction, the mixture is treated with crushed ice and acidified with well cooled 10% HCl. The precipitated styrene derivative is collected and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 123°-124°. (Found: N, 14.32. $C_8H_8O_4N_2$ requires N, 13.43 per cent.).

It was not found possible to reduce this compound to the amine under investigation.

My thanks are due to Dr. J. N. Rây for his kind interest in the work.

